

Ferrocene-derived ligands and their reactions with titanium, organotitanium, zirconium and organozirconium compounds

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Reactions of 1-formylferrocene-4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (HFfmbh) and 1-acetylferrocene-4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (HAfmbh) with $\text{TiCl}_4(\text{thf})_2$, $\text{ZrCl}_4(\text{thf})_2$ (thf = tetrahydrofuran), $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_3$, $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OMe})$, $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OMe})_2$ and $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{ZrCl}_2$ yield complexes of the types $(\text{Lig})_2\text{TiCl}_2$, $(\text{Lig})\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$, $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Lig})_2\text{X}$, $\text{Ti}(\text{Lig})_2\text{X}_2$ and $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Zr}(\text{Lig})_2\text{Cl}$ (where HLig = HFfmbh and HAfmbh; X = Cl and OMe). Reaction of $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ with LiMe in benzene yields dimethyl derivative $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiMe}_2$, while that of $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ with PhMgBr in the affords organotitanium(III) species $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ph})\text{thf}$. On the other hand, reactions of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$, also synthesized in this study, with MeSH, $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{NMe}_2)$, $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{N}_3)$ and $\text{Me}_3\text{SiC}\equiv\text{C-Ph}$ afford $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{L}^1$ (where $\text{L}^1 = \text{SMe}$, NMe_2 , N_3 and $-\text{C}\equiv\text{C-Ph}$). Both the ligands function in a monobasic bidentate fashion in the complexes and the deprotonated enolic form of the ligand is involved in the coordination to the metal.

Currently much interest has been shown on the complexing behaviour of organometallic ligands including ferrocene-derived ligands¹⁻⁴. A search for readily oxidisable ferrocenyl ligands has added a further incentive to studies in the field, as the ferricinium ions possess antitumour activity, whereas the parent ferrocene does not^{2a}. The activity of platinum and gold complexes⁵ of 1,1'-bis(diphenylphosphino)ferrocene (Fdpp) against experimental tumours has been reported. However, Fdpp complexes are not readily oxidised⁶. The syntheses of oxidisable ferrocenyl ligands would allow the design of multifunctional drugs. Enhanced antibiotic activity of penicillin and cephalosporine has been noted by replacing aromatic groups with the ferrocenyl moiety⁷.

The enzyme inhibiting properties of hydrazone ligands have been reported⁸. The tuberculostic properties of hydrazides and their derivatives have been extensively studied⁹ and the condensation products of hydrazides with different carbonyl compounds are known to be less toxic than the parent hydrazides; and this is probably due to blocking of the free amino group.

As comparatively few reports are available on metal complexes of ferrocene-derived ligands¹⁻⁴, we initiated a study on the topic and as a part of that study we have investigated the reactions of 1-formylferrocene-4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (HFfmbh) and 1-acetylferrocene-4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (HAfmbh) with $\text{TiCl}_4(\text{thf})_2$, $\text{ZrCl}_4(\text{thf})_2$, $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_3$, $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OMe})$, $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OMe})_2$ and $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{ZrCl}_2$ and isolated many new organotitanium and organozirconium derivatives. The reactivity of some of the newly synthesized organoderivatives has been explored leading to newer syntheses of many

more new organotitanium and organozirconium compounds. This paper also describes the reactions of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$, synthesized in the present investigation, with MeSH, $\text{Me}_2\text{NSiMe}_3$, Me_3SiN_3 and $\text{Me}_3\text{SiC}\equiv\text{CPh}$.

Results and Discussion

The syntheses of aroylhydrazones, 1-formylferrocene-4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (HFfmbh) and 1-acetylferrocene 4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (HAfmbh) have been described earlier⁴.

Reaction of HFfmbh or HAfmbh with some organotitanium(IV) and organozirconium(IV) compounds, TiCl_4 and ZrCl_4 yielded a large number of new organoderivatives of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) which are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1. The organotitanium(III) complex $[(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ph})\text{thf}]$ has also been isolated.

The reactivity of the Ti-Cl bond in complex $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**1**) with different substrates was studied leading to the syntheses of many new organotitanium(IV) derivatives. Thus **1** on reaction with MeSH in thf-toluene(Et_3N) gave $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})(\text{SMe})$ (**9**). Similarly, **1** reacted smoothly with $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{NMe}_2)$, $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{N}_3)$ and $\text{Me}_3\text{SiC}\equiv\text{CPh}$ in a mixed solvent system and afforded amino-, azido-, and phenylethynyl complexes of organotitanium(IV) $[(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{L})]$ [where L = NMe_2 (**10**), N_3 (**11**), or $-\text{C}\equiv\text{CPh}$ (**12**)] as shown in Fig. 2.

Desilylation of the reagents is the driving force of the above reactions. Since the by-product Me_3SiCl is a low boiling liquid and miscible with common organic solvents, it is easily removed by low pressure distillation. Hence, the new organometallic compounds of the type $[(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{L})]$ were obtained in very pure form and good

yield. Treatment of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{NMe}_2)$ (**10**) with SnPh_3H in thf gave a solution from which a brown solid compound $[(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{SnPh}_3)]$ (**13**) could be isolated.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the organotitanium(IV) and organozirconium(IV) compounds*

Compd.	Mol. wt. ^a Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % :		ΔM^b $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ mol^{-1}
		Cl	Ti/Zr	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (1)	865	4.10	5.60	4.9
$(\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{TiCl})$	(870.3)	(4.08)	(5.50)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{OMe})$ (2)	849	-	5.82	5.1
$(\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$	(865.9)		(5.83)	
$\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{OMe})_2$ (3)	850	-	5.91	5.8
$(\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$	(831.9)		(5.76)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Afmhb})_2\text{Cl}$ (4)	915	3.96	5.63	7.9
$(\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{43}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{TiCl})$	(898.4)	(3.95)	(5.33)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Afmhb})_2(\text{OMe})$ (5)	900	-	5.55	8.0
$(\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$	(893.9)		(5.36)	
$\text{Ti}(\text{Afmhb})_2(\text{OMe})_2$ (6)	880	-	5.92	14.8
$(\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$	(859.9)		(5.57)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Zr}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (7)	898	3.90	9.99	10.2
$(\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{ZrCl})$	(913.7)	(3.88)	(9.98)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Zr}(\text{Afmhb})_2\text{Cl}$ (8)	958	3.80	9.66	12.4
$(\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{43}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{ZrCl})$	(941.7)	(3.77)	(9.68)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{SMe})$ (9)	868	-	5.18	11.8
$(\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{TiS})$	(881.9)		(5.43)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{NMe}_2)$ (10)	892	-	5.88	11.2
$(\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{45}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$	(878.9)		(5.45)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{N}_3)$ (11)	-	-	5.66	14.5
$(\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$			(5.46)	
$(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{C}\equiv\text{CPh})$ (12)	-	-	5.08	14.2
$(\text{C}_{51}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti})$			(5.12)	
$(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (14)	831	8.45	5.76	14.8
$(\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{TiCl}_2)$	(840.9)	(8.44)	(5.70)	
$(\text{Afmhb})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (15)	842	8.20	5.69	14.5
$(\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Fe}_2\text{TiCl}_2)$	(868.9)	(8.17)	(5.51)	
$(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$ (16)	966	7.51	9.71	14.2
$(\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{Fe}_2\text{ZrCl}_2)$	(956.2)	(7.42)	(9.54)	
$(\text{Afmhb})_2\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$ (17)	-	7.32	9.30	14.8
$(\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{Fe}_2\text{ZrCl}_2)$		(7.21)	(9.27)	
HFfmbh	356	-	-	-
$(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Fe})$	(361.9)			
HAfmhb	382	-	-	-
$(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Fe})$	(375.9)			

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, and N analysis. ^a Rast's method. ^b 10^{-3} M solution in DMSO.

Fig. 1

Complex **13** is unstable in air and decomposes on heating at 245–250°. Reaction of $\text{TiCl}_4(\text{thf})_2$ with HFfmbh and HAFfmbh in thf- Et_3N proceeded smoothly yielding $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (**14**) and $(\text{Afmhb})\text{TiCl}_2$ (**15**), respectively. Similar reaction of $\text{ZrCl}_4(\text{thf})_2$ with the above ligands afforded $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$ (**16**) and $(\text{Afmhb})_2\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$ (**17**), respectively. Reaction of $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (**14**) with

Fig. 2. Reactions of $[(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}]$ (**1**).

LiMe in C_6H_6 yielded dimethyl derivative $[(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiMe}_2]$ (**18**), while reaction of **14** with PhMgBr in thf afforded an organotitanium(III) species $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ph})(\text{thf})$ (**19**). Compound **18** can be stored under nitrogen atmosphere at 0–10° for 2 to 3 days. It decomposes very easily. Such dimethyl compound should be extremely reactive as a consequence of the autolabilization effect of the two methyl groups. Compound **18** decomposed in solution at room temperature. Compound **19** is also not stable under ordinary laboratory conditions. All the other complexes are stable under laboratory conditions. All of the isolated compounds are coloured yellow to brown.

The elemental analyses of the complexes agree well

with their formulations (Table 1). The molecular weights (measured by cryoscopic or Rast's method) are also in good agreement with the theoretical values. Both the ligands are soluble in methanol, chloroform and dimethylsulfoxide, while the metal complexes are soluble in coordinating solvents like dimethylsulfoxide, dimethylformamide, pyridine and also in other solvents like chloroform and methanol. All the complexes are insoluble in *n*-hexane and ether. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMSO solutions (10^{-3} M) show very low values, in the range of 4.9–14.8 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹ (Table 1), indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

The UV-vis spectral band observed in the 260–270 nm region in both ligands and complexes is due to the B-band of the cyclopentadienyl ring (the complexes show a small bathochromic shift)^{10,11}. The broad band at about 450 nm, due to a charge-transfer transition between the cyclopentadienyl ring and the iron atom of the ferrocenyl moiety, was observed in very close position both for the ligands and the complexes^{10,12a}. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition bands for the ligands were observed at 295–300 nm but in the complex this band was shifted to higher frequency by about 15 nm. This indicates an increase in conjugation in the complexes¹⁰. Besides, most of the organotitanium(IV) compounds showed a new band at 460–410 nm in addition to the bands discussed above, and may be ascribed to charge transfer¹³ bands in accordance with the titanium(IV) configuration. The complexes are all diamagnetic in nature.

Both the ligands, HFfmbh and HAFfmbh showed bands due to ν_{N-H} at 3310 and 3220 cm⁻¹, respectively. The band due to $\nu_{C=O}$ for the ligands appeared at 1640–1636 cm⁻¹. These bands were absent in the complexes, suggesting the enolisation of the ligands during complexation³. This is also supported by the fact that no band for OH in the spectra of the ligands and also in the complexes were observed, instead, a band due to ν_{C-O} (1280–1220 cm⁻¹) was observed for the complexes, which also supports the above observation. The above facts suggest that the ligands remain in the keto form in the solid state but in solution, both the keto and enol forms may remain in equilibrium¹⁴, and during complexation deprotonation occurs from the enol form.

The free ligands also showed a strong band at 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N), which was shifted to a lower value by about 10 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, demonstrating coordination of imine-N to the metal ions^{2b,10,11}. Besides, a sharp band observed at 1628–1600 cm⁻¹ in the complexes can be attributed to the stretching mode of the azine chromophore (C=N–N=C)^{3,15}.

The characteristic bands for the ferrocenyl group appearing in the ligands remained almost unchanged in the complexes^{10,16}. In addition to the bands for the ferrocenyl

group, the complexes showed bands at about 3105 and 1032 cm⁻¹, attributable to the π -bonded cyclopentadienyl group¹⁷. Also the bands for ν_{Ti-N} and ν_{Ti-O} appeared at 520 and 606 cm⁻¹, respectively, which are tentative assignments.

¹H NMR spectra support the conclusions derived from spectroscopic study discussed above. The ligands HFfmbh and HAFfmbh exhibited two peaks at δ 4.2 (s) and 4.8 (br), assigned to proton signals of unsubstituted and substituted cyclopentadienyl rings of the ferrocene moiety¹⁸, respectively. Aromatic protons signals appeared at δ 7–7.8 (m). Signals for the NH protons appeared at δ 10.8–11.15 (s,br), which disappeared in the complexes, indicating, thereby, the coordination of the ligands to the metal ions in the enolic form after deprotonation^{2b}. In addition to the signal at δ 3.65 (s) for (s, O-Me), ligands HAFfmbh displayed a signal at δ 2.21 (s, = C-CH₃)^{2,19}.

In the complexes (in DMSO-*d*₆) the aromatic proton signals appeared downfield, as expected, due to increased conjugation during coordination¹⁹. But there is no appreciable change in the chemical shifts of ferrocenyl protons on chelations¹⁸. Correct integrations are consistent with the formulae. The sharp signals for S-CH₃, and N(CH₃)₂ protons in the complexes **9** and **10** suggest *trans* arrangements. The aromatic proton signals in complex **12** appeared around δ 6.8–8.0 (m) and its correct integration supports the formulation of the said complex.

Experimental

1-Formylferrocene and 1-acetylferrocene (Fluka and Sigma) were used as such. Titanium tetrachloride and zirconium tetrachloride were commercial products and used as such. Compounds (π -C₅H₅)TiCl₃, (π -C₅H₅)TiCl₂(OMe) and TiCl₂(OMe)₂ were prepared by literature methods²⁰. (π -C₅H₅)₂ZrCl₂ was prepared by literature method²¹. Other chemicals and solvents were purified and dried by standard procedures before use. The elemental analyses were carried out at the R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Physical measurements were carried out as described earlier^{4,22}.

The ligands HFfmbh and HAFfmbh were prepared by reported methods⁴. The complexes were synthesized in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

The methods (i) and (ii) were used to study the reactions of organotitanium(IV) compounds with HFfmbh or HAFfmbh.

(i) To a solution of HFfmbh or HAFfmbh (0.001 mol) in dry chloroform (80 cm³) was added a fresh, hot solution of (π -C₅H₅)TiCl₃, (π -C₅H₅)TiCl₂(OMe), or TiCl₂(OMe)₂ (0.0005 mol) in dry chloroform (80 cm³) with stirring. The mixture was then refluxed at neutral pH for 8 h and filtered while hot. The reddish brown filtrate was concentrated in a

rotary evaporator and *n*-hexane was added with stirring to yield reddish brown to yellowish brown precipitates of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**1**), $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{OMe})$ (**2**), $\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{OMe})_2$ (**3**), $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Afmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**4**), $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Afmbh})_2(\text{OMe})$ (**5**) and $\text{Ti}(\text{Afmbh})_2(\text{OMe})_2$ (**6**). The compounds were filtered, washed with dry EtOH and *n*-hexane and dried under reduced pressure, yields 65–75%.

(ii) A mixture of solution of HFfmbh or HAFfmbh (0.001 mol) with the above mentioned organotitanium(IV) compound (0.0005 mol) in dry chloroform was stirred at room temperature in the presence of a stoichiometric amount of Et_3N for 3 days and then filtered. From the resulting brown solution, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain a solid mass. To the solid was added EtOH (~60 cm³) and the mixture was stirred and filtered. The residue was washed thoroughly with ethanol and recrystallised from chloroform-*n*-hexane (40 : 60, v/v) and dried under reduced pressure, yields ~60–75%.

Similarly, the reactions of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ with HFfmbh or HAFfmbh were carried out in thf-toluene mixture in 1 : 2 molar ratio yielding brown $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Zr}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**7**; 70%) and $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Zr}(\text{Afmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**8**; 68%).

The reactions of TiCl_4 and ZrCl_4 with the ligands HFfmbh or HAFfmbh were performed in dry thf at room temperature and in the presence of stoichiometric amounts of Et_3N in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The resulting yellow-brown filtrate gave $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (**14**), $(\text{Afmbh})_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (**15**), $(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$ (**16**) and $(\text{Afmbh})_2\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{thf})$ (**17**) in ~60% yield.

Reactions of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**1**) :

Reaction with MeSH : A mixture of $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2\text{Cl}$ (**1**; 1 mmol) and MeSH (1 mmol) in thf-toluene (50 : 50 v/v; 50 cm³) was stirred at room temperature in the presence of a stoichiometric amount of Et_3N for 4 days. Solid $\text{Et}_3\text{N.HCl}$ separated was removed and volume of the solution was reduced under vacuum. The solution was cooled (~10°) to give brown solid $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{SMe})$ (**9**), which was washed with *n*-hexane and dried under reduced pressure, yield 75%.

Reaction with $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{NMe}_2)$: Complex **1** was heated with an equimolar quantity (1 mmol) of $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{NMe}_2)$ as before in the same solvent system (60 cm³) to yield $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{NMe}_2)$ (**10**; 70%).

Reaction with $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{N}_3)$: Brown solid $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{N}_3)$ (**11**) was isolated by the reaction of **1** and $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{N}_3)$ (1 : 1 equivalent) in thf for 3 days; and the usual work up, yield 50%.

Reaction with $\text{Me}_3\text{SiC}\equiv\text{CPh}$: Similarly, compound **1** (1 mmol) on treatment with $\text{Me}_3\text{SiC}\equiv\text{CPh}$ (1 : 1 equivalent) in thf, yielded light brown $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{Ffmbh})_2(\text{C}\equiv\text{CPh})$ (**12**; 50%).

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References

1. M. Yongxiang and B. Gang, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **144**, 1265; Z. Xiaoxian, L. Youngmin, N. Fajun and M. Yongxiang, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**, 447; S. P. Singh and N. B. Singh, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 557; S. R. Patil, U. N. Kantak and D. N. Sen, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **68**, 1; H. Iami and T. Ota, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 2497; K. Dey and K. K. Nandi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 633, 908; S. K. Srivastava, B. K. Srivastava, N. Gupta, O. P. Pandey and S. K. Sengupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 778, and references cited therein.
2. A. Houlton, J. R. Dilworth, R. M. G. Roberts, J. Silver and M. B. Drew, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 275; Z. Gang, L. Feng, X. Jishan and M. Yongxiang, *Polyhedron*, 1988, **7**, 303.
3. S. R. Patil, U. N. Kantak and D. N. Sen, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **63**, 261.
4. K. Dey and K. K. Nandi, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1999, **29**, 419.
5. B. Longato, G. Pilloni, G. Valle and B. Gorain, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 956; D. T. Hill, G. R. Girard, E. L. McCabe, R. K. Johnson, P. D. Stupik, J. H. Zhang, W. M. Reiff and D. S. Eggleston, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 3529.
6. B. Gorain, B. Longato, G. Fanero, D. Ajo, G. Pilloni, U. Russo and F. R. Kressi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **157**, 259; A. Houlton, J. R. Millu, R. M. G. Roberts and J. Silver, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 2181.
7. E. I. Edwards, R. Epton and G. Marr, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1975, **85**, c-23.
8. J. C. Craiz, J. C. Rubo, D. Willis and J. Edger, *Nature (London)*, 1955, **176**, 34.
9. N. P. Buu-Hoi, N. D. Xuong, N. H. Nam, F. Binon and R. Royer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1358.
10. M. Yongxiang, Z. Zhengzhi, M. Yun and Z. Gang, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **165**, 185.
11. S. I. Goldberg, D. W. Mayo and J. A. Alford, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1708.
12. (a) M. Mosenblum, J. O. Santer and W. G. Gowell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1450; (b) W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
13. S. Kumar and N. K. Kaushik, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2679.
14. K. Dey and D. Bandyopadhyay, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 267.
15. K. S. Biradar and V. H. Kulkarni, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 2451.
16. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
17. G. Doyle and R. S. Tobias, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1111.
18. M. D. Rausch and A. Siegel, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1969, **17**, 117.

Dey *et al.* : Ferrocene-derived ligands and their reactions with titanium, organotitanium, zirconium *etc.*

19. Z. Hong-Yun, C. Dong-Li, C. Pei-Kun, C. De-Ji, C. Guang-Xia and Z. Hong-Quan, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**, 2313.
20. K. Dey, S. B. Ray and D. Koner, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1983, **92**, 257; K. Dey, D. Koner, A. K. Biswas and S. B. Roy, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1982, 911.
21. P. C. Wailes, R. S. P. Coult and H. Weigold, "Organometallic Chemistry of Titanium, Zirconium and Hafnium", Academic, New York, 1974.
22. K. Dey, R. Bhowmick, S. K. Nag, K. Chakroborty and S. Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 427.